

Hypertension and Auditory function: Evaluating the Effects of Medication on Auditory Impairment

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Abstract

Introduction: Hypertension, characterized by persistently elevated blood pressure, is linked to various health complications, including hearing loss. That a rise in blood pressure directly affects hearing. The anterior aspect cerebellar arteries, basilar arteries, and both of their branches deliver blood to the inner ear. These arteries split in the same manner as the cochlear artery and the posterior vestibular arteries. Hypertension-related high blood pressure may cause haemorrhages inside those capillaries. A microvascular deficit in the cochlea, brought on by embolism, vasospasm, or haemorrhage, can result in hearing loss. This study aims to evaluate the effects of hypertension and its medication on auditory function.

Methods: Participants aged 21-60 years with normal hearing and diagnosed hypertension was included. Auditory assessments, including immittance audiometry, pure tone audiometry (PTA), and distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAE), were conducted.

Results: Significant differences were observed in all frequencies tested (PTA & high frequency) between the control and hypertension groups in both ears. Additionally, DPOAE results indicated lower signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) in hypertensive individuals, particularly after long-term medication usage exceeding 5 years. Furthermore, drug duration beyond 5 years was associated with a significant decrease in SNR, suggesting a detrimental effect on cochlear health.

Conclusion: The study highlights the importance of monitoring auditory function in hypertensive individuals and considering the duration and type of medication in managing hearing health. These findings underscore the need for further research to elucidate the mechanisms underlying hypertension-related hearing loss and to develop targeted interventions for individuals with hypertension. Overall, this study contributes to our understanding of the relationship between hypertension, medication, and hearing loss, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive audiological assessments and tailored management strategies for hypertensive patients.

Keywords: Hypertension, Hearing Loss, DPOAE, Extended High Frequency, Duration of Drugs

Introduction

Hypertension, also known as systemic arterial hypertension, is characterized by consistently high blood pressure in the systemic arteries. Blood pressure, measured as the force exerted by blood on artery walls during heart contraction and relaxation, is represented by two numbers: systolic and diastolic. The thresholds for identifying hypertension vary depending on measurement techniques. Primary hypertension, affecting 90-95% of individuals, has multifactorial causes [1]. Define blood pressure ranges, with primary hypertension often influenced by complex gene-environment interactions.

Hypertension, characterized by a persistent blood pressure above 140/90 mmHg, is closely associated with hearing loss due to various physiological mechanisms. The condition can lead to increased blood viscosity, impeding capillary blood flow and oxygen transfer, resulting in tissue hypoxia, which in turn can affect auditory function. Moreover, elevated blood pressure in the vascular system poses a risk of inner ear damage, potentially causing hearing loss through ionic changes and alterations in microcirculation, accelerating degeneration within the inner ear. Additionally, hypertension-induced damage to the inner lining of arteries may lead to thrombus formation, obstructing blood flow and causing cell death in distant regions, further contributing to sensorineural hearing loss. Prolonged hypertension and the accumulation of fat in damaged arteries can also result in atherosclerosis in cochlear arteries, heightening the risk of hearing impairment, particularly in individuals with a large waist circumference and high body mass index (BMI). Furthermore, acute sensorineural hearing loss, although often reversible, can occasionally become irreversible, with drug use-particularly ototoxic medications-linked to impaired oxidative metabolism, tissue hypoxia, and compromised capillary blood flow, exacerbating hearing issues. [2].

Loop diuretics, such as those affecting the cochlea by inducing edematous gaps in the stria vascularis epithelium, have immediate consequences on the endolymphatic system, leading to the loss of cochlear potentials. Excessive blood pressure, a contributing factor, can manifest early on with symptoms

akin to heart failure and visual impairment. Both primary and secondary hypertension can present warning signs like low vision, dizziness, tinnitus, and vertigo. Given the global impact of systemic arterial hypertension on millions of individuals, there's growing concern among medical professionals regarding its direct link to hearing loss. Evidence suggests that hypertension affects blood supply to the inner ear through various arteries, potentially leading to microvascular deficits, altering cellular ionic balance, and causing tissue hypoxia. While acute hypertension may protect the cochlea from arterial injury, untreated hypertension can lead to irreversible harm, including compromised endo-cochlear potential and the development of conditions like pulsing tinnitus and hearing loss. Additionally, research indicates hypertension's direct impact on vestibular organs, contributing to various complications beyond auditory impairment. According to [3], hypertension most likely had a bigger effect on central vestibular system impairment. Hypertension triggers a cascade of physiological changes in blood vessels, including increased production of collagen and elastin by smooth muscle cells, leading to hypertrophy and hyperplasia. This process thickens the arteries, potentially damaging their lining as blood rushes in with elevated pressure, causing plaque expansion and impeding blood flow. Hearing loss, which can manifest suddenly or gradually with hypertension, often involves inner ear complications like hemorrhage. Microorganisms in cortical organs may induce hair cell reduction, while neuropathy can stem from microangiopathy and atrophy of nerve fibers and ganglia. Accumulation of harmful compounds from endolymph metabolism, compounded by arterial obstruction around the endolymphatic sac, can further contribute to hair cell atrophy. The Blood-Labyrinth Barrier (BLB) within the cochlea plays a crucial role in maintaining fluid and ionic balance, potentially disrupted by hypertension-induced vascular changes, affecting the inner ear's health and function. [4]

Hearing loss poses a significant global health challenge, impacting individuals and society by hindering communication and social interaction, often resulting in social isolation. Research underscores the substantial burden of hearing impairment worldwide, with millions affected, including 63 million in India and over 700 million globally. Older individuals bear a disproportionate share, with 54% of those over 65 experiencing hearing loss. Studies also reveal correlations between hearing loss and

cardiovascular risk factors like cholesterol and diabetes. While medication treatments for hearing loss remain limited, controlling risk factors assumes paramount importance for prevention. Vascular damage, possibly linked to elevated blood pressure, may contribute to hearing loss by compromising oxygen delivery and inducing tissue hypoxia. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for developing effective prevention and management strategies, particularly given the scarcity of pharmacological interventions and reliance on clinical devices for therapy.

Aim of the Study

The aim of the current study was to assess the impact of various drug kinds that were administered to people with hypertension on hearing loss.

Objective of the Study: To compare the effect of different drugs on Oto-acoustic emissions & the impact of the duration of drug usage on hearing sensitivity at standard frequencies (500 Hz, 1 kHz, and 2 kHz) and extended high-frequency hearing sensitivity (9 kHz & 12 kHz).

Materials & Methods

This study aimed to evaluate the effects of various drugs on oto-acoustic emissions at various frequencies and explore the correlation between the length of drug use and hearing sensitivity at standard frequencies (500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz) and extended high-frequency (9 kHz, 12 kHz) hearing sensitivity. This study was approved by SRM MCH & RC (IRB No: 2440/IEC/2021)

Inclusion criteria for the study encompass individuals aged 21 to 60 with normal hearing, undergoing hypertension medication for over a year. Additionally, diagnosed hypertension patients without significant co-morbid conditions affecting hearing are eligible. These criteria ensure a focused investigation into the long-term effects of hypertension treatment on auditory health. On the other hand, exclusion criteria entail individuals with a history of otitis media or auditory neuropathy being included, while those with medical conditions like diabetes, kidney disorders, heart problems, or systemic illnesses impacting auditory function were excluded. This meticulous selection process aimed to isolate the effects

of hypertension and its medications on hearing, thereby providing clearer insights into the relationship between hypertension and hearing loss.

Procedure & Instrumentation

The assessment protocol for participants in this study was designed to comprehensively evaluate their auditory health. It begins with a thorough case history and otoscopic examination, providing valuable insights into participants' medical backgrounds and identifying any potential ear abnormalities. Following this initial assessment, a 512 Hz tuning fork test were administered to further assess auditory function and differentiate between conductive and sensorineural hearing loss. This test serves as a crucial step in the diagnostic process, helping to guide subsequent evaluations. Immittance audiometry using GSI Tymstar Pro was conducted to assess middle ear function, providing essential information about the integrity of the tympanic membrane and the mobility of the ossicular chain. Subsequently, conventional audiometry (PTA) and high-frequency audiometry (HFA) were performed to measure hearing thresholds across a range of frequencies, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of participants' hearing abilities. Finally, oto-acoustic emission (DPOAE) testing was employed to evaluate the function of the cochlear outer hair cells, providing valuable insights into cochlear health and function. By incorporating these various assessments into the evaluation protocol, this study aimed to provide a thorough and accurate assessment of participants' auditory health, facilitating precise diagnosis and appropriate treatment planning.

Statistical analysis

The results of the pure tone audiometry test were documented. Version 22 of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to export the data. The Independent t test was used to assess the significant differences in mean scores between the two groups for each of the criteria.

Results

70 subjects were involved in the study, split into two groups. Group I (control) and Group II (hypertension) each had 35 individuals. Participants in both groups ranged in age from 21 to 60. The experimental group of people with hypertension had an average age of 50.80 ± 8.66 years, while the control group of adults without hypertension had an average age of 29.24 ± 6.91 years. All the subject included in the study were undergone for detailed audiological case history taken and immittance audiometry to rule out the middle ear status.

Figure 1: Gender distribution of adults

Above Fig (1) showed that, were 24 women and 11 men in the group of people with hypertension. There are 21 men and 14 women in the adult non-hypertensive group (Fig 1).

*Table 1: Comparison of hearing thresholds between control group and hypertension group in right ear** $P < 0.05$

Frequency (Hz)	Control Group I (N=35)	Hypertension Group II (N=35)	P-Value
500Hz	11.57 ± 3.59	27.57 ± 15.40	0.000*
1 Khz	13.0 ± 3.25	28.0 ± 14.96	0.000*
2 Khz	12.43 ± 4.26	32.57 ± 16.60	0.000*
9 Khz	11.86 ± 7.96	75.00 ± 22.94	0.000*
10 Khz	14.14 ± 8.08	77.71 ± 20.12	0.000*
11 Khz	14.29 ± 9.08	81.43 ± 16.69	0.000*
12 Khz	15.71 ± 9.08	85.71 ± 12.25	0.000*

The mean values of all the frequencies (500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz & 9 kHz - 12 kHz) of control and hypertension groups in the right ear. All the frequencies noticed that, a significant difference ($P < 0.05$). The comparison was done by using Independent “t” test to calculate the mean value (Table 1).

Table 2 Comparison of hearing thresholds between control group and hypertension group in Left ear

Frequency (Hz)	Control Group (N=35)	Hypertension Group (N=35)	P-Value
500Hz	11.86 ± 3.44	27.43 ± 13.02	0.000*
1 Khz	12.57 ± 4.26	27.86 ± 12.67	0.000*
2 Khz	12.00 ± 3.67	31.14 ± 13.83	0.000*
9 Khz	10.57 ± 9.68	74.29 ± 23.76	0.000*
10 Khz	12.43 ± 8.52	77.29 ± 19.75	0.000*
11 Khz	12.57 ± 10.31	81.57 ± 16.39	0.000*
12 Khz	13.57 ± 9.43	85.86 ± 11.72	0.000*

The mean values of all the frequencies (500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz & 9 kHz - 12 kHz) of control and hypertension groups in the Left ear were reported. Across all the frequencies, there was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$). This comparison was done by using Independent “t” test to calculate the mean value (Table 2).

Table 3: Comparison of Mean SNR values of OAE between the control group and hypertension group for higher frequencies (8 kHz- 10 kHz)

Frequency (Hz)	Ear	Control group (n=35)	Hypertension group (n=35)	p-value
	R.E	10.74 + 4.99	.81 + 3.92	0.000*
8 kHz	L.E	11.14 + 4.58	.84 + 4.04	0.000*
	R.E	10.35 + 7.27	.73 + 4.16	0.000*
9 kHz	L.E	10.24 + 4.98	.71 + 4.61	0.000*
	R.E	10.60 + 4.79	.83 + 4.19	0.000*
10 kHz	L.E	10.33 + 5.35	.30 + 4.56	0.000*

$p < 0.05^*$

Independent “t” test was performed to compare the SNR of the control and experimental group for higher frequencies (9 kHz - 12 kHz), there is a 5% level of significance was observed in both ears separately. Table 3 shows that, there is a significant difference ($P < 0.05^*$) between control and hypertension group across three frequencies (8 kHz - 10 kHz) in both ears separately. The above table shows that there was a significant difference seen in each frequency across all duration of the gap in the both ears. The significance is more as the duration increases in all frequencies (Table 3)

Figure 2: Comparison of SNR (OAE) between the hypertension groups on the duration of drugs in the right ear.

The above analysis reveals a significant difference in Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emission (DPOAE) results associated with the duration of drug usage, particularly beyond 5 years, in the right ear. This prolonged medication period appears to exert a notable impact on auditory function, indicating potential cochlear changes over time due to antihypertensive drug therapy. These findings underscore the necessity for longitudinal studies to elucidate the long-term effects of hypertension medication on hearing health and inform tailored management strategies for individuals undergoing prolonged treatment.

Figure 3: Comparison of SNR (OAE) between the hypertension groups on duration of drugs in the left ear.

The analysis revealed a significant difference in Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emission (DPOAE) results associated with the duration of drug usage, particularly beyond 5 years, in the left ear. This prolonged medication period appears to exert a notable impact on auditory function, indicating potential cochlear changes over time due to antihypertensive drug therapy. These findings underscore the necessity for longitudinal studies to elucidate the long-term effects of hypertension medication on hearing health and inform tailored management strategies for individuals undergoing prolonged treatment.

Discussion

Comparing the current study to control groups, it shows that people with hypertension have hearing loss in both ears at low, mid, and high frequencies up to 12 kHz. Between the control and hypertension groups, there is a statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in all frequencies (Tables 2 and 3). Each member of the hypertension group received a diagnosis of mild to severe sensorineural hearing loss in both ears, depending on their level of impairment. Furthermore, only a small number of studies claimed that hearing loss, which is frequent in people with hypertension, is permanent and reversible. Additionally, there are differences in the severity of sensorineural hearing loss (30% mild-moderate).

There is a connection between hearing loss and hypertension in the hypertensive person according to [3], [4], [5], [6], [7].

In this study, the DPOAE test (objective) was administered to both groups at three distinct frequencies (8 - 10 kHz) in order to examine the inner ear functioning. These DPOAE SNR value results were contrasted with those of the control group. Additionally, Table 3 shows that the DPOAE values were statistically significant ($P = 0.000$) between the groups at all three frequencies. When compared to the hypertension group, the SNR value of the control group was less than 6 dB, despite being higher than 6 dB. The DPOAE test showed statistically significant ($P=0.01$) results at high frequencies, as demonstrated by the current investigation (Table 3). Furthermore, there is a scant evidence in research linking inner ear impairment to hypertension. The connection between systemic arterial hypertension-induced microvascular alterations and inner ear impairment. because of microvascular alterations that cause SNR values to drop [5], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. The current study found that among patients with arterial hypertension, hearing thresholds had a considerable sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) at high frequencies as a result of lower DPOAE (SNR values) [6],[8],[9],[12]

The current study looked at which factors had a greater impact on the length of the drug's effect 1-5 years, 6-10 years, and 11-15 years. On the other hand, when the drug's duration grows, DPOAE findings show that hearing loss occurs concurrently in both ears (SNR values). Nonetheless, in individuals with bilateral hypertension, the influence of medication treatments is shown in the high frequency hearing threshold. Furthermore, medications had an identical impact on both ears at high frequencies this study coincide to [9], [5], [13], [14].

Clinical implications of the study

The findings of this study hold significant clinical implications, providing a valuable tool for monitoring hearing sensitivity in patients undergoing treatment for hypertension, particularly concerning the duration of medication use. The observed progression of sensorineural hearing loss from higher to lower frequencies underscores the importance of early detection and intervention. Importantly, the study

highlights the critical role of Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emissions (DPOAE) as a clinical technique for identifying high frequency hearing loss in individuals with hypertension. Leveraging the standard DPOAE examination can aid in the timely recognition and tracking of hearing loss development in hypertensive patients, facilitating proactive management and enhancing overall patient care.

Limitations of the study

We have found that the groups in our study had an unequal distribution of gender and age. The age range of the hypertension group was larger, indicating more age variability within this group. Furthermore, we didn't evaluate the impacts of drug use by doing pre- and post-comparisons. This implied that we were unable to assess the long-term effects of medicine on hearing function. These drawbacks point to areas that future studies should focus on to gain a deeper understanding of the connection between medicine, hypertension, and auditory health.

Conclusions

The inner ear's delicate structure, reliant on intricate blood vessels and hair cells, is vulnerable to the impact of hypertension, which can cause gradual or sudden hearing loss by damaging its blood supply. Recent research examined the influence of various blood pressure medications and their duration on hearing in adults aged 21 to 60. The study found that long-term medication use among hypertensive individuals correlated with increased hearing loss, particularly at higher frequencies, with certain medications exacerbating issues, notably between 8 and 12 kHz as indicated by otoacoustic emissions tests. These findings highlight the complex interplay between high blood pressure, specific medication types, and hearing loss, stressing the need for effective hypertension management to safeguard hearing health.

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